

THE ROLE OF SENTENCING FOR CRIMES WITH PLEA AGREEMENTS IN THE PENAL SYSTEM

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Abstract.

The concept and significance of plea agreements, their socio-legal necessity, historical development, and some practical issues related to sentencing are discussed, with proposals and recommendations provided. To reliably ensure citizens' rights and freedoms, the essence of sentencing for crimes with plea agreements is clarified, opinions on some practical issues are expressed, and proposals are developed.

Keywords: Guilt, confession, agreement, punishment, right, freedom.

Recent reforms in our republic's sentencing system aim to strengthen the principles of humanism, justice, and legality. These reforms focus on increasing the effectiveness of crime prevention, protecting human rights in sentencing, and ensuring transparency in judicial processes.

Today, one of the pressing issues is revising the system of punishments and their implementation mechanisms, morally rehabilitating individuals found guilty of crimes, and introducing types of punishments and other legal measures aimed at preventing potential crimes.

Within the framework of this research, determining the place of sentencing for crimes with plea agreements in the overall sentencing system, as introduced in the legislation, is a key issue.

Chapter XI of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan is titled "Sentencing," outlining the grounds for sentencing and circumstances to be considered. Article 54 of the Criminal Code contains the following provision regarding general grounds for sentencing: "A person found guilty of committing a crime in accordance with the procedure established by law shall be punished. The court, within the limits established by the article of the Special Part of this Code providing for liability for the committed crime, assigns punishment in accordance with the provisions of the General Part."

When imposing punishment, the court takes into account the nature and degree of public danger of the committed crime, the motive of the act, the nature and amount of damage caused, the personality of the guilty party, and the circumstances mitigating and aggravating the punishment.

The absence of general grounds for sentencing in the criminal legislation of some developed modern states (for example, England, Germany, and other countries), and the fact that such grounds are defined in the criminal legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan itself, indicates that the principles of humanism and democracy of criminal law can serve as an example.

In scientific sources, the general principles of sentencing and the principles of sentencing are considered as closely related concepts, since the principles of sentencing

largely serve the functions of these principles[2]. In doing so, the authors assess the general principles of sentencing as fundamental ideas enshrined in the norms of criminal law, applied by the courts as the main guidelines for imposing a just and appropriate punishment on each accused, and draw attention to their interrelationship.

Within the framework of this issue, it is useful to cite the views put forward by A.S. Yakubov and other authors on the general principles of sentencing. In their opinion, "the general grounds for sentencing are derived from the norms of criminal legislation and constitute a system of legal guidelines based on the principles of the Criminal Code, on the basis of which the court determines the type and measure of punishment applied to a person found guilty of committing a crime"[3]. As can be seen from this definition, the views of A.S. Yakubov and others on this issue are more consistent with practice. Because courts rely on these general principles when sentencing persons who have committed crimes.

For additional information, it can be said that Article 54 of the Criminal Code clearly defines the general grounds for sentencing, according to which a person found guilty of committing a crime in accordance with the procedure established by law is subject to punishment. According to the Criminal Code, the court assigns punishment in accordance with the rules of the General Part, within the limits specified in the article providing for criminal liability in the Special Part.

Adherence by the courts to these general principles in the determination of punishment ensures the appointment of a lawful and just punishment to the person who committed the crime. At the same time, the authors, relying on legislation, separately identify various elements in the system of general principles of sentencing.

In legal science, researchers include a number of cases in the system of general grounds for sentencing. For example, F.M. Mingalimova added the following to the list of general grounds existing in criminal legislation: a) the fairness of punishment; b) the imposition of punishment in accordance with the provisions of the General Part of the Criminal Code; c) the establishment of punishment in compliance with the norms of the Special Part; d) the application of a more severe type of punishment only if it is impossible to achieve the goals of punishment provided for by law; e) the court's consideration of the nature of the crime and the degree of danger to society; f) the personality of the person who committed the crime; g) the influence of the imposed punishment on the correction of the convict and his family situation.

We also fully agree with the opinion of the renowned scholar M. Rustamboev that "The socio-political essence of punishment depends on the state's policy of combating crime, and this policy depends on the legal ideology, political, economic, cultural, moral, and other influential views and perceptions in society" [5].

The unjustified imposition of a severe punishment creates in the subject a sense of dissatisfaction with injustice, distrust of justice and the law. It is also appropriate to say that such a situation also becomes an obstacle to achieving the goal of punishment[6].

S.V. Borodin emphasizes that the general grounds for sentencing consist of the criteria that should be applied by the court when sentencing each defendant for a specific crime.[7]

A.V. Kladkov defines the general grounds for sentencing as the basic requirements that must be fulfilled by the court for each crime, regardless of whether the crime was committed individually or in complicity, when assigning any type of punishment.[8]

Z.M.Salihov proves that general grounds are manifested as basic legislative guidelines of universal significance and at the same time perform the function of specific technical rules, that is, they determine the "technique" of applying general regulatory rules for each specific case of sentencing, that general grounds do not automatically determine the grounds for sentencing and its individualization, but indicate to the court what circumstances should be taken into account in this process[9]. G.K.Buranov and L.R.Valeva emphasize that "general grounds for sentencing are primary in relation to its specific rules. A change in the former inevitably leads to a restructuring of the entire structure of the latter. If a specific rule contradicts the general principles of sentencing, it must be repealed." [10] Thus, special rules for sentencing should not contradict the general rules, but rather clarify them, should not bypass the general rules.

Summarizing the above norms and opinions, the general principles of sentencing serve as legally established criteria applied by the court in each criminal case. These grounds allow the court to determine the appropriate type and measure of punishment for a person found guilty of committing a crime. The principles of sentencing are considered a broader concept than general principles, as they apply to all aspects of judicial activity. The general principles of sentencing are taken into account only when sentencing a person found guilty within the framework of a specific criminal case.

Although the system of punishment, types, and general rules for sentencing are widely and comprehensively covered in legal literature, the issues of sentencing for crimes for which a plea agreement has been concluded have not been sufficiently studied. Theoretical and practical issues regarding sentencing have been studied in considerable detail. This includes numerous textbooks, commentaries on the law, monographs, and other works dedicated to the analysis of the norms of the Special Part of the Criminal Code. At the same time, scientific research devoted to the problems of the institution of sentencing in our country is becoming increasingly relevant today. However, at the same time, in these studies, the problems of sentencing for crimes for which a plea agreement has been concluded were not studied collectively.

When imposing punishment, the court takes into account the nature and degree of social danger of the committed crime, the motive of the act, the nature and amount of damage caused, the personality of the guilty party, and the circumstances mitigating and aggravating the punishment. This norm is also established in paragraph 3 of Resolution No. 1 of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 3, 2006, "On the Practice of Sentencing by Courts." Some authors consider each of the circumstances taken into account in sentencing as an independent element of the general grounds for sentencing.[11]

In the case of actual repentance of the guilty party, the imposition of punishment is determined by Article 571 of the Criminal Code: "In the presence of mitigating circumstances provided for in subparagraphs "a" and "b" of part one of Article 55 of this Code, and in the absence of aggravating circumstances provided for in part one of Article 56 of this Code, the term or amount of punishment cannot exceed two-thirds of the maximum punishment provided for in the corresponding article of the Special Part of this Code. This rule does not apply to persons who have committed crimes related to premeditated murder under aggravating circumstances (part two of Article 97) and terrorism (part three of Article 155)." As can be seen from the disposition of the article, a plea agreement differs from a plea agreement based on actual remorse for one's actions. However, there is a common similarity

between them. That is, it would not be an exaggeration to say that the institution of practical repentance for one's actions is the first manifestation of a plea agreement.

In the scientific literature, opinions have been expressed about comparing the imposition of punishment for crimes for which a plea agreement has been concluded with the imposition of punishment when the guilty party actually regrets their actions.

I.E. Zvecharovsky, in his views, drew attention to the socio-legal significance of the institution of imposing punishment on the basis of a plea agreement. In his opinion, this institution is associated with positive steps, such as the sincere repentance of the guilty party, assistance in solving the crime, or assistance in the investigation. In a certain sense, this is analogous to such institutions as voluntary renunciation of the commission of a crime or active repentance. A common feature of these mechanisms is that first a beneficial action is expected from the guilty party, and then a corresponding social and legal result arises, although the quantity and nature of these results do not fully coincide.

However, Zvecharovsky also shows the difference between these institutions. For example, voluntary renunciation or remorse can take effect immediately after the commission of the crime, that is, immediately, regardless of whether the crime was completed or not. The plea agreement takes effect only after the person is officially recognized as a suspect or accused and a special agreement is signed with them. These points are an important point of his analysis on this topic."[12]

N.N. Kirillova agrees with I.E. Zvecharovsky on the similarities and differences between the plea agreement and the institution of practical remorse for guilt and adds the following thoughts: "Practical remorse of the guilty party is the basis for both exemption from criminal liability and reduction of punishment. This institution can be implemented both at the preliminary investigation stage and in court. Fulfillment of the conditions of the plea agreement only entails positive criminal law consequences at the trial stage of the criminal proceedings."[13]

At this point, one cannot disagree with I.E. Zvezharovsky's opinion that a plea agreement is analogous to practical remorse for guilt[13].

The conducted research, having studied the similarities and differences between sentencing under a plea agreement and sentencing under a plea agreement when the guilty party actually regrets their actions, as a common feature, firstly, in both institutions, admission of guilt is considered an important element, that is, in both cases, the person admits responsibility for their actions; secondly, mitigation of punishment, that is, in both cases, the court, taking into account the actions of the accused, can mitigate the punishment; thirdly, the legal consequences in both cases serve the interests of the accused. The main differences, in terms of content, are that in the case of practical repentance of guilt, the person actually repents of their actions and realizes the consequences of their criminal act, and in the case of a plea agreement, the person admits guilt, but this is considered more as a legal agreement than personal repentance. The first arises in the process of sentencing by the court, and the second arises during the preliminary investigation, and the conclusion was made that it requires the creation of an official document.

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